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Lesson of Inclusive Education Implementation in Jakarta: Availability and Accessibility Issues

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Abstract

Inclusive education is believed to be an innovative educational approach that can promote the educational opportunities for all children with special needs including those with disabilities. It also stresses the principle of human right, social justice and quality of education for all. The institution education has an obligation to making education available and accessible particularly for children with special needs. This article will provide an overview of availability and accessibility issues concerning inclusive education program in public school Jakarta. The study formed within qualitative research and uses a case study as strategy research for the collection and analysis of data. Semi-structured interview with the government, schools, parents, and NGO have been conducted to analyse the implementation of inclusive education in Jakarta in terms of availability and accessibility at both primary and secondary level. The result of this research revealed that there is an inadequacy in the provision of facilities and personnel to adequately prepare the children with special needs in the inclusive education program and the inequality of accessibility to basic education services between institutions. It thus called for intervention in the education sector of the region, if the goal of education for all is to be realized. There is also a discussion of recommendations and conclusions that may assist in supporting inclusive education in Jakarta.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Availability, Innovative, Accessibility, Special needs, Disabilities

Introduction

A growing body of research on inclusive education in the past decade provides solid evidence regarding what works and what does not work in attempting to include Special Education Needs students in general education classrooms and schools (Clark et al. 1995, Lipsky and Gartner 1997, Pijl et al. 1997, Vlachou 1997, Booth and Ainscow 1998, Thomas et al. 1998, Ballard 1999). Inclusive education is a new paradigm in the discourse on the Indonesian education system. Inclusive education is a system to accommodate all the children education based on their needs and their ability (Bergsma, 2000; Crippen, 2005; Eleweke and Rodda, 2002). Previously, children with special needs were looked like a child with specific characteristics, and they needed a special approach to education based on their characteristics (Sunaryo, 2009). Tarsidi (2011) also stated that from 1950 to 2003, education in Indonesia followed a segregated system where normal and disabled children studied in separate schools. Regular school is a general school which is provided by the government for normal children. The level

of regular school provided from elementary until higher education. Meanwhile, the children who have physical or mental impairments studied in special schools, called extraordinary schools.

Following to support this program, the Ministry of Education assigned the General Directorate of Special Education to implement an inclusive education program. In 2009, the Indonesian government through the Ministry of Education issued a regulation (70/2009) about inclusive education practices. The regulation stipulates that for each municipality there should be at least have one primary school and one junior high school per district area and one secondary high school or vocational school per municipality. Regarding Tarsidi (2011), this regulation was issued by the government as a way to support access for children with disabilities and the gifted/ talented to get an adequate education in a school nearby where they lived. At the global level, contemporary educational policy privileges a managerial model of school rather than a model that emphasises the sociocultural purposes of schooling that would support inclusive communities (Goldstein 2004; Slee 2007; Tamatea 2005). There is considerable empirical evidence that children with disabilities were once seen too vulnerable to be educated in regular classrooms and many believed that they needed to be sheltered in special settings (Kavale and Forness 2000). Special interventions or placement options would be determined based on the specific diagnosis of disabilities to treat students' deficits (Vaughn et al. 2000).

In Indonesia, the operation of inclusive education is based on the following principles: 1) equality and the improvement of quality; inclusive education is a philosophy and strategy to gain equal access to educational services and improve the quality of education for all children, with respect for diversity; 2) diversity and individual differences in terms of abilities, talents, interests, and needs of the student participants; education should be pursued to meet the needs and characteristics of individual learners; 3) meaningfulness; inclusive education should create and maintain a welcoming classroom community, receive diversity, and respect the differences and independent learning of all learners; and 4) sustainability; sustainable, inclusive education should be conducted for all types of lines and levels of education. A number of issues and contradictions arise when we scrutinise rules that explicitly state a criterion for eligibility. According to the legislation education in Indonesia, the education process not only the government responsibility but also other institutions such as parents and communities. The success of inclusive education implementation could be seen from how the government and other institutions collaboration and coordination. Based on Tarsidi (2011) research about the education system in Indonesia proposed that the government and other institutions have obligations to make education available, accessible, acceptable and adaptable for all their citizens.

Tarsidi, (2011) said that "The development of inclusive education in Indonesia is indeed a bit left behind compared to the progressive implementation of inclusive education in other countries. It is seen in the limited resources, knowledge, and skills required for the successful implementation of inclusive education. The existing curricula of general education have yet to accommodate the different needs of children with disabilities fully". It gives general information about behaviour management around the school and in the classroom. Indonesian organizations and national governments have committed themselves to the inclusive development of education at least at the level of rhetoric. However, there were still many schools that had not restructured their school organizations. Sunardi et al. (2011), documented that only about 58 percent of schools reported having modified their instructional program, but most schools lacked appropriate equipment, media, or resources for SEN. It is hard to imagine modifying instruction to meet the individual needs of SEN without adequate media and resources.

Indonesians in general and educators specifically need to acknowledge that inclusive education is part of the human rights agenda that argues that all children, irrespective of their characteristics, can learn and have access to education. Availability which is a condition of being available, especially of being attainable (Merriam Webster Dictionary), is one of the ways to ensure all students have access to an appropriate and suitable education in order to reach their full potential. In education, according to UNESCO. (2005), argued that the availability in education could be meant as a social condition where people can access education easily. Currently, as a new program, the implementation of inclusive education in Jakarta still faced availability issues such as funding, teachers and facilities, and infrastructure. Rewards and incentive issues for teachers, who have

an additional task in teaching, facilities have not been adjusted for children capabilities and needs, are not accordance with the basic concept of inclusive education (Ombudsman, 2009).

Furthermore, accessibility can be viewed as the possibility of accessing the resources of some system or entity by all. It is important for all stakeholders within the school community to be aligned. Accessibility to basic educational attainment has been identified as a major indicator of human investment in the nation (Hanmer et al., 1998). As a result, Indonesia have to recently consider the vision that all schools should have the capacity to accommodate the needs of all learners in their community, by highlighting the need for good architectural designs to facilitate effective natural and artificial illumination in classrooms and buildings, modification of facilities, and redesigning the physical landscape of schools to promote accessibility and use for all children, regardless of disability. Investment in education for human nations is related significantly with economic growth and social development. Increased investment in human capital, especially in education, is essential for the achievement of the millennium development goal because education is the foundation for sustainable lifelong individual development.

In education, accessibility is often referred to some vulnerable group such as people with disabilities, gender, the minority, and internally displaced and how to get their right to access that system (UNESCO, 2005). Inclusive education is the way to accommodate vulnerable groups. In the Universal Declaration in Article III on "Universalizing Access and Promoting Equity" stated that educational disparities existed and that many different particular groups were vulnerable to discrimination and exclusion. These included girls, the poor, street and working children, rural and remote populations, ethnic minorities and other groups, and mention was made of people with disabilities. Therefore, this article will discuss the availability of inclusive education with through three factors namely: budget allocation, teacher welfare, and school facilities and infrastructures and two themes were analysed from the data as issues to make the implementation of inclusive education program in Jakarta accessible namely: no discrimination in education system and safe physical reach.

Indonesia Education System

The forms of Indonesia's education system have two dimensions, namely, track and level. Formal, non-formal and informal are three types from the track point of view. The dimensions of the level are consists of basic education, secondary education, and higher education. Basic education level constitutes a 6-year primary school, 3-year junior secondary school. The secondary level has two types of school namely: a senior secondary school which offers more academic-oriented programs and vocational secondary school is more vocational skills. Both, are directed continue to higher education, but for vocational graduates can enter to the labour markets. The detail features are presented in table 1 below.

Informal education track, there are general schools and Islamic school. The general schools are managed by the Ministry of National Education and for the Islamic school, since the curriculum put more emphasis on Islamic teaching, are managed by the Ministry of Religious Affairs. At primary level, the general one is called Sekolah Dasar (SD), while that at junior level is called Sekolah Menengah Pertama (SMP), and Islamic one is called Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs) and for senior school level is called Sekolah Menengah Atas (SMA) and Madrasah Aliyah (MA) for Islamic school.

Table 1: Indonesia's Education System

Level	Track	School	Age of schooling
Basic Education	Formal	1. Primary School 2. Islamic Primary School (Madrasah Ibtidaiyah)	7 – 12 years old
		1. Junior Secondary School 2. Madrasah Tsanawiyah	13 – 15 years old

	Non-Formal	Package A	7 – 12 years old
		Package B	13 – 15 years old
Secondary Education	Formal	1. Senior Secondary School 2. Vocational Secondary School 3. Madrasah Aliyah	16 – 18 years old
	Non-Formal	Package C	
Higher Education		Universities/ Institute 1. Non-Degree Program (Diploma I –IV) 2. Degree Program (Bachelor, Master, and Doctorate) 3. Professionals program equals to master and Doctorate	19 – 29 years old

In the higher education level, Indonesia has two tracks namely university and institute. The differences in the name on the program which they are offers. The university offers different disciplines, such as economics, law, science, art, agriculture, etc. Meanwhile, the institute only offers one type of disciplines such as technology or education. Each discipline has branched out into different specialities. For example, education may be branched out into technology education, sports education, art, and language education. It also occurs in technology as a discipline, and it may be branched out into processing technology, information technology. Both of that higher education level are offer degree and non-degree program. The degree program started from Strata 1 which is equal with Bachelor, strata II equal with Master degree and Strata III equal with Doctorate. The non-degree program is range from diploma I until diploma IV. The detail forms are presented in table 1 above.

In addition, Indonesia's education system recognizes non-formal education as a means of ensuring education provisions for citizens. This track is especially to eradicate literacy as well as to provide education children for children due to geographic isolation, and social exclusion are left out from education provision. Package A, B, and C are the non-formal programs which have to make a significant distribution to achieve the target of the compulsory of 9-year basic education.

Particularly, for disabled children, the government provided special schools based on the type of impairments. The special schools (SLB) are divided into some groups namely: SLB A is for children with visual impairment; SLB B is for children with hearing impairment, SLB C for children with developmental impairment, SLB D for children with physical impairment, SLB E for children with social and emotional disorder and SLB G for children with multiple impairments.

The Challenge for Teachers in Inclusive Education?

The use of term inclusive education has become widespread. UNESCO (2005) described inclusive education as an educational process where all the learners will learn together based on their diversity of needs and reducing exclusion in education. It involves changes, modifications in content, approaches, structures, and strategies, with a common vision which covers all children of the appropriate age range and conviction.

Stainback and Stainback (1990) defined that an inclusive school is a place where all students are learning together with their peer in the same class. This school provides decent education programs, challenges, but execute based on the abilities and needs of students, and support by the teachers to make them succeed in the learning process. Therefore, inclusive education not only focused on children with special needs but also to all children who have a problem in learning. That is true that one of learning barrier was influenced by disabilities, but there was another factor such as emotional and environmental factors. On the other hand, inclusive is not a fixed concept, and it is the result of social construction which depends on the context and needs understanding based on the topic discussed (Florian, 2006). Additionally, in inclusive education, the challenge for teachers is the quality of learning and participation of all the pupils located therein. Inclusive schools are understood to be those that make major adjustments to their organisation and processes in response to their diverse populations. A key element of adjustment is in the way that teachers teach: to develop inclusive pedagogy teachers need access to good information.

Previous systematic literature reviews related to the area of SEN and inclusion had focused on behavioural concerns and behaviour management in schools (Harden et al. 2003); the impact of paid adult support on the participation and learning of pupils in mainstream schools, including pupils with SEN (Dyson, et al. 2003); and school-level approaches to facilitating the participation by all students in the cultures, curricula and communities of schools (Nind, 2006). Although research had sought to establish the effectiveness of particular pedagogies or the impact of school actions on pupil participation, there had been no prior systematic review that could answer the question of what pedagogical approaches can effectively include children with SEN in mainstream classrooms. In this regards, also there is considerable evidence that teachers attempt to differentiate their teaching according to perceptions of broad pupil ability. Martin and Hayes, (1998) reported that general and specific ability were among the enduring characteristics which teachers perceived as important when planning to teach. Similarly, Clark et. al (1995), exploring teachers' 'craft knowledge' in relation to the teaching of 11-12 year-olds, found that response to pupils perceived as being of low ability included emphasising oral explanations, providing multiple examples, using pictorial stimuli and, for pupils with writing difficulties, providing highly structured written tasks. These strategies cannot be taken as necessarily representing either a common or a SEN-specific pedagogy. The starting point for this review is to take the pedagogic justification for such differentiation as problematic and uncertain (Brahm and Anne, 2013).

Inclusion can be seen as a process to respond to the diversity among all individuals through participation in studying, culture and society and diminished exclusion in education services (Booth, 1996; Florian, 2006). However, a growing number of psychologists and educators believe that culturally biased tests are a factor in unwarranted special education placements. For example, in his review of Renato et al., (2009), links the practices of an earlier period with the continuing salience of race. Families of children with disabilities are insisting on the placement of their children in general education classrooms, with the necessary supplementary aids and support services. Thus, the discourse in special and general education about who is to be educated and about how they are to be educated provides an opportunity to examine these relationships in society at large. But interestingly, inclusion today is about the children who are not in school, children in school whose needs are not being met, the teachers in the schools, the legal system, the social culture, and the education system itself (Watkins, 2009), and the policy fails to recognize the differences between pupils with special needs (Turner, 2003).

With regard to the place where disabled children received their education, Cigman (2007) opines that there are two different opinions. The first opinion is the opinion of the Universalist who is advocated for systemic change related to universal inclusion. The Universalist argues that mainstream schools should welcome and adapt themselves to all children without exception. The second opinion comes that from the moderate who generally agrees with the Universalist, but with the caveat that this must be subject to the school's capability in terms of school resources. Based on these two opinions, it is important to ensure that every school can provide the right amount of education. But, it is established that the culture of each school is dependent on the attitudes of staff and their professional ideologies (Handy and Aitkin, 1986). As a result, Carrington, (1999), in their observational analysis of pupils, found that all teachers involved were more concerned with controlling pupil behaviour than ensuring pupils were working effectively.

Turning to the benefits of inclusive education, inclusive education can help disabled children avoid the negative labelling of a special school. Some researchers believed that children in a special school might feel humiliated (Margalit, 1997). Margalit defines humiliation as 'any behaviour of condition that constitutes a sound reason for a person to consider his or her self-respect injured' (p.2). This opinion is in line with the statements of the Centre for Studies in Inclusive Education (CSIE) as stated below:

"The discrimination inherent in segregated schooling offends the human dignity of the child... Segregated schooling appeases the human tendency to negative label and isolates those perceived as different. It gives legal reinforcement and consolidation to a deeply embedded, self-fulfilling, social process of de-valuing and distancing others on the basis of appearance and ability in order to consolidate a sense of normality and status" (Education, undated).

Inclusive Education in Jakarta

The policy of including pupils with special educational needs (SEN) in mainstream schools and classrooms in Indonesia becomes complex issues. The legal basis for the implementation of inclusive education in Jakarta was strengthened by the issuance of governor regulation no. 116/ 2007 regarding the implementation of inclusive education. Chapter III article 4 of this regulation stated that at least 3 primary schools and one junior high school should have existed in every sub-district together with one senior high school in every district. Nowadays, there are 161 schools implementing inclusive education in Jakarta (Regional Education office of Jakarta data, 2009). It consists of three pre-schools, one hundred and twenty primary schools, thirty-one for junior level and ten schools for secondary level. The number of these inclusive schools is not compatible with the governor regulation no. 116/ 2007. Jakarta has five regions and one district with forty-four sub-districts. Thus, based on that regulation the amount of inclusive school at the primary level should be one hundred and thirty-two, at the junior level, forty-four schools and at the secondary level is fifteen schools (Fuadi, 2013). Table 5.1 showed the number of Inclusive school by the district in Jakarta.

Table 5.1: Number of Inclusive School by District in Jakarta, 2010

Education Level (Year)	North Jakarta	East Jakarta	Centre Jakarta	West Jakarta	South Jakarta	Total
Primary (1 – 6)	15	41	20	19	25	120
Secondary (7 – 9)	6	8	5	6	6	31
High (10 – 12)	2	2	2	2	2	10

Based on the table above, see that primary school which conducted inclusive education is more than secondary and high school namely if 75% (120 schools) of 161 inclusive school in Jakarta. The school distributed evenly in that entire district. The amount of school in secondary and high school is not as much as primary school. There are many reasons related to this condition. First, the government is concerned with nine years compulsory education program which stated that all Indonesian people is required to go to school for nine years in the basic level of education; six years in primary school and three years in secondary school. It will give a significant impact on the implementation of inclusive education. Second, inclusive education is a new education program in Indonesia that means the education institutions still looking for a better concept to implement this program.

The research result of inclusive education assessment in Jakarta by Ombudsman (2009) also founded that there are some components in the implementation process that are not in accordance with the basic concept of inclusive education, such as: 1) curriculum that the school used is not adapted to the needs of children, 2) supporting teacher or shadow teacher is not provided in every inclusive school, 3) facilities have not been adjusted for children capabilities and needs, 4) admissions process through the online system is not relevant to the needs of student.

The governor of Jakarta realised the importance of democracy and equality access in education for all learners with any condition, and this is also in line with the demands of human values particularly related with the human right to obtain a quality education (Sunaryo, 2009). Based on the governor regulation above, the aim of inclusive education implementation in Jakarta are: a) to increase the understanding of human diversity in democratic society, b) to give an appropriate education based on human right, c) to make education accessible for all children with special needs. This regulation also means that all the public school which has been assigned as an inclusive school by the government have to accept children with special needs to learn together with their peers (Brahm & Anne, 2013).

Methodology

The researcher, in the present study, to address the research objectives and research questions adopts a qualitative approach. The qualitative research has a various and different meaning. Qualitative research can be viewed as a solution integrated with a set of practice and arranged clearly to solve the problems in real situations (Denzin & Lincoln, 1994). According to Patton (2002), qualitative research is a research that produced and processed descriptive data, such as; interview transcripts, field notes, pictures, and video recording. In qualitative research, the researcher pressed on the relationship with people who involved in this study. The purpose of this act is to get a better understanding of real life. (Taylor, & Bogdan, 1998) stated in qualitative approach researcher will know the subject (person) personally and analyse them how they develop their own definitions of various things., Through a qualitative method is expected to emerge the actuality, reality, and subject perception without formal measurements as described in Mason (2002).

Research Strategy

This research will use the case study as strategy research. Robson (2002, p.178) defines a case study as 'a strategy for doing research which involves some empirical investigations of a particular contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context using multiple sources of evidence.' Therefore, this strategy can be used to achieve a better perceptive of the research context and existing processes (Mason, 2002). The case study will bring us to the understanding of a complex issue or object in real life. As like as Patton (2002) defined that case study is 'a design employed to gain an in-depth understanding of the situation and meaning for those involved. The interest is in the process rather than outcomes, in context rather than a specific variable, in discovery rather than confirmation. She concluded, 'the single most defining characteristic of case study research lies in delimiting the object of study of the case' (p.27).

In this research, I will use the case study as my research strategy. Because this research focussed on inclusive education program and used multiple sources that included individuals and institution particularly in education. The aim of this research is analysing the implementation of inclusive education in Jakarta with institutionalized poverty challenges. Inclusive education is a National Education Program which focussed on children with learning disabilities. This child is studying in a regular school together with their peers.

Data Collection

The data collection for this study was conducted for 4 months in Jakarta. Jakarta as the main city in Indonesia is composed of 5 districts, namely; centre, east, west, north, and south of Jakarta. Each of districts has some inclusive school from primary school, secondary school until high school. In this research, I will choose the school based on two criteria; school location and the level of education. Each of the districts will be represented by five schools as follow; three primary school (including school model), one secondary school and one high school.

Participants

Participants in this study were non-probability sampling selected. Purposive sampling is a form of non-probability sampling. Denzin and Lincoln stated that 'many qualitative researchers employ...purposive and not random, sampling methods. They seek out groups, settings, and individuals where the processes being studied are most likely to occur (1994, p.202).

The participants in this study are coming from educational institutions which consist of government, school, and communities (parent and NGO). Two people were represented from Directorate of Special Education and Special Education Services in the Ministry of National Education. They served as a head of curriculum areas for special education unit and as a head of assessment and accreditation education program for special education

unit. In the regional level, the head of the special education unit in Education Office Jakarta is becoming my participant in this research.

In the inclusive school, the participant consists of principals and teacher. The teacher who participated in this study is a class teacher and supporting teacher or shadow teacher. They consistently worked closely with the inclusive education program. From the communities, this research interviews the parents who have children with special needs in inclusive school and also parents who have normal children and one Non-Government Organisation (NGO) that one of their programs is developed the inclusive school in Indonesia. This organisation is Helen Keller Indonesia (HKI) which has sponsored from the Helen Keller Foundation in the United States. HKI and the Indonesian Government collaborated in inclusive education program since the year 2000 until now.

Results and Discussions

This study explored inclusive education for children with special needs in Jakarta related to availability and accessibility issues. The findings are described as follow;

Availability Issues

In educational institutions, availability can be defined as a social condition where people can access education easily because education is a human right (UNESCO, 1990). Education for all (EFA) is a declaration of the United Nations that has the goal that all children without exception can get access to school and be educated at least through the primary level. There are three themes that emerge in this situation, namely: budget allocation, teacher welfare and facilities, and infrastructures.

Budget Allocation

One of the considerations in the implementation of inclusive education is a concern with the availability of financing and supporting resources (Lynch, 2001). As one of the government program in the education sector, inclusive education needs additional funding where it will blow the education budget and increase the unit of cost provision. It is common sense that those children with special needs will require additional resources because they need more educational equipment's to support the learning process. McLaughlin & Warren (1994) determine that inclusion is expensive to implement at the first stage, but it should become cost-effective over time. This is also supported by (Peter et al., 1999) who stated that inclusive education is a golden opportunity to reduce the cost of special education services which is more expensive than regular education.

Relating to the cost of inclusive education program, the Indonesian government issued a policy that the government will provide funding for school which implemented inclusive education. This situation explained by a participant that:

"Resources funding for schools to implement inclusive education can get this from the Department of Education in Jakarta or General Directorate of Special Education." (Gov3)

However, this participant also gives an additional explanation that government funding will stop when the school stop continuing this program:

"When they are stopping that program, no will be more fund for them in the next term." (Gov3).

Regarding some participant from schools about the funding from the government, they used the funding to:

The grant was used to conduct a workshop in 2009 for the teacher, student's representative and also people who lived near that school as participants. The aim of this workshop is to introduce an inclusive education program" (ScH1)

"we used the funding from the government to buy learning materials for some types of a student with special needs in this school." (ScP1).

Some schools not only got funding from the government but also from another source such as non-government organization, communities, and universities.

"... this school has cooperated with Paramadina University since 2008, and always participated in any workshop conducted by region office and other universities, such as Jakarta State University (UNJ)". (ScP2)

"... this school has cooperated with HKI to provide free glasses for those who have a problem with far sight last year". (ScJ1)

According to the condition of the inclusive education program in Jakarta, we can see that the government in the national and regional level supported the implementation of that program. Support is provided through allocated funding for inclusive schools. The school can also get funding from other institutions such as non-government organization, communities or other parties which concerned with the inclusive education program.

Teacher Welfare

The researcher found that teacher welfare in the implementation of inclusive education in Jakarta particularly become very fundamental issues. Teacher welfare has become a key point of education availability. The teacher has to receive competitive salaries, enjoy better working conditions, have access to teaching materials and get an offered join in training programs to improve their teaching abilities and increase their involvement in the learning process (Skipper, 2006).

Additionally, this research has shown that educators play as an important role to make the inclusion program run smoothly, yet, there are problems related to managing inclusion class. Therefore, the government has to provide some training or workshop as a way to achieve teacher competence in the learning process. As stated by Riggs and Mueller (2001) that intensive and systematic training, given by competent and experienced trainer, is suitable for the inclusive teacher. The research found that an international NGO has collaborated with the Indonesian government to conduct a basic understanding of inclusive teaching. As stated by the participant from secondary school,

"our teacher in this school received training of trainers' program which is held by HKI and also some workshops conducted by State University of Jakarta." (ScH2)

The other issues that have been found are the lack of support personnel to help teachers. Support teacher together with the class teacher to make a lesson plan, review lessons and share ideas in teaching children with special needs in mainstream class. From 27 schools which become sample in this research, there are 18 inclusive schools don't have support teacher. The main constraint faced by either at schools or in the Regional Education Office is associated with supporting teacher status.

"The status of supporting teacher is still not admitted as a permanent teacher, there is a time when the Department of Education in Jakarta comes to our school to register all teachers, but in the register form, there is none for the supporting teacher, then my status always as a subject teacher who is not fit for us." (SupT1)

"When I have to fill in the occupation form from the Department of Education in Jakarta, I can't find my status as a supporting teacher in one of the choices. (SupT2)

This condition will impact the incentives and awards that they should receive as a non-permanent employee in schools. As stated by participants from primary school:

We paid supporting teacher salary with this funding, but we did not mention them specifically, because there is no item for supporting teacher cost in that proposal and they are not allowed to do that." (ScP2)

With regards to the description above, the issue of supporting teacher status in Jakarta is still a problem in Indonesia, particularly in Jakarta. This problem will have an impact on their income and their future career. We can see that support teachers are an important part making this program successful because the function of supporting the teacher is helping the class teacher in making lesson planning and evaluation (Hanmer, 1998). This issue remains unresolved by the government. The reason is that there is no regulation to accommodate the status of supporting teachers in the school structure and the budget of education items.

Facilities and Infrastructures

Since 2000, the implementation of inclusive education in Jakarta faced facilities and supporting infrastructure issues. Most the public schools in Indonesia, particularly in Jakarta have standard structure building for a regular student.

"The problems that we are still facing even now are the standard of the building structure. In general, the building structure in public schools is built like a standard building for the normal student; none of the public schools are built for the purpose of disabled children. Example of building structure issues

include: there is no toilet for disabled children in all schools, and also no lift for a student with wheelchairs." (Gov2)

Nevertheless, regarding the Department of Education in Jakarta, there is a school that had the initiative to modify the stairs to give access to their student with a wheelchair.

"We have a student with cerebral palsy. The government gave us a wheelchair to support it. And we also modify our school stairs so that student can have access to go to the upper floor." (ScJ2)

Pivik et al., (2002) stated that resources are the main causes of the schools' unreadiness to conduct inclusive education in some countries. It is not easy to change the school systems from regular school to inclusive school without any suitable facilities that support the teaching and learning process. Besides, school creativity to fulfil the implementation of inclusive education needs a school capacity (Hanmer, 1998).

Regarding school facilities, such as learning materials and other supporting equipment, government or NGO which concerned with this program help schools to provide it.

"We have a student with visual impairments, and then the government provides us with some Braille books." (ScJ3)

"...that the fund obtained from the General Directorate of PSLB is used to buy Braille Letters". (ScJ4)

"... this school has cooperated with HKI to provide free glasses for those who have a problem with far sight last year". (ScJ1)

"... there is a special English exam for the blind and the deaf from the region officer." (ScH2)

This problem is not only faced by Indonesia but also with other countries. There is some research about the issues of school facilities of inclusive schools which still became a major problem in some countries (Porter, 2001; Skipper, 2006). Therefore, the coordination among education institutions which is related to this program is that it is important to develop inclusive education programs in a better way that is appropriate for all the students.

Accessibility Issues

Accessibility can be viewed as the possibility to all individuals to access resources of some system or entity. Accessibility to basic educational attainment has been identified as a major indicator of human investment in the nation (Harden et al., 2003). Two themes were analysed from the data as issues to make the implementation of an inclusive education program in Jakarta accessible. First, no discrimination in the education system which means the government as a decision maker should provide legislation that supports all vulnerable children to access education easily, and for schools to provide quality education services for all the children without exception. The next theme is about safe physical reach. This means that besides the school location which has to be close in their area regardless of their strengths, weakness, and disability (Booth, 1996).

No Discrimination in Education System

Inclusive education emphasizes on giving access to education for those who have special educational needs. The main factor based on the access to inclusive school is the requirement system from schools to accept children with special needs. This research founded that requirement process for students with special needs in primary school is conducted in two stages. First is administration selection and then, interview with parent and student. In the first stage, students have to provide some documents such as a medical report from professionals (psychologist) who state that they have the ability to learn in regular school along with other supporting documents.

"In 2010 the registration process in inclusive school for the parent who had a child with special needs have to apply a week before recruitment of regular student. The new student should bring a recommendation letter from their psychologist and the result of an IQ test and also other documents such as birth certificate and family identity card." (ScJ2)

The statement above is also agreed with by another participant from primary school who added:

"In this school, we have 35 children with special needs including students with learning difficulties. 15 of them enrolled through the special registration process, and the rest of them were found after the learning process passed" (ScP4)

The recommendation letter from a psychologist is compulsory for children with special needs if they want to enrol into regular school, as stated by a supporting teacher from Primary School:

“There is no special criterion for children with special needs to enrol in this school. As long as they have the recommendation letter from their psychologist which mentions that this child can study together with other normal children in regular school, then this school will accept them. We also conducted IQ tests collaborated with a special clinic or psychologist for students who indicated a need for special education.”(ScP5)

Meanwhile, the inclusion idea appeared in most nations which are related to education and individual rights particularly for children with a special need to be educated in mainstream schools (Peters 2004). This means that the education systems have to support children with special needs to enter the regular school without any condition because they also have the same rights that other children have to be educated.

Safe Physical Reach

The friendly environment and access to the school is a pre-requirement process to implement in inclusive education in regular schools.

“Ideally, children should go to schools that are nearby. Therefore, we appointed schools evenly in each district in Jakarta.” (Gov3)

The problem is that faced by the government relating to the distance of school issues has come from that school itself. In most developing countries, the issues of limited inclusive school arise as a lack of government policy to make inclusive education accessible for all children (Clark et al. 1995). This means that for children with special needs who live far away from inclusive school will not be able to get a chance to study in inclusive schools or they should spend additional costs to reach that school.

“We had a blind student last year, but he has now moved to another school which is closer to his house. Fortunately, this year the government has appointed some senior high schools as an inclusive school but not as much as primary schools.” (ScH2)

There are some schools, although appointed by the government to implement inclusive education; nevertheless, they refused to conduct that program. They argued that they are still not yet ready with the supporting facilities to implement that program. This is also expressed by the participant from the government sector:

“, before The Ministry Regulation no. 70, 2009 issue about inclusive education which stated that in each district they have at least one primary school and one junior high school and at least 1 senior high school or vocational school in each municipality, we have already appointed some schools in any level for each district in Jakarta to be an inclusive school. But, most of them still rejected this because they felt they were not ready to implement it yet. That is why the number of inclusive school in Jakarta still insufficient.”(Gov3)

But after that, through the Ministerial Regulation number 70/ 2009 about the implementation of inclusive education, there are no more arguments from schools to conduct that program. The regulation stated clearly that the government would appoint some school to implement inclusive education. The result of this regulation based on the data in 2009 and 2010 about the total amount of inclusive education is increasing from 54 inclusive schools in Jakarta to 161 schools. These views were also expressed by one of a parent from Primary School

“Before 2009, I have a problem in finding an inclusive school for my child. But now, I heard from my friend that there are many inclusive schools in Jakarta and I am really glad to hear that.”(Pa2)

However, the goal is to make the implementation of inclusive education in Jakarta a success. This encourages all institutions to strive for better than success.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Overall the implementation of inclusive education in Jakarta is still not run optimally. From the availability point of view, seemingly the budget allocation system by the government needed a review. Teachers need service training to improve their competence to manage the learning process particularly for children with special needs. Supporting teachers required clarity from the government regarding their status in schools. Currently, some schools put supporting teacher status as teacher class in order to give incentives and rewards. The inabilities of schools to provide and to accommodate adequate infrastructure and facilities for a student with special needs such as toilet for disabling or access stairs for a wheelchair, however, coordination and collaboration between school, parents, and communities may be needed.

Regarding the accessibility issues, it can be concluded that educational institution which in this case consists of: government, schools, and communities still need more efforts to make education accessible for all the children including children with special needs. The result of this research, confirm that: the implementation of inclusive education in Jakarta concentrated on providing opportunities for disabled children to attend regular schools while ignoring other issues such as ethnicity, victims of natural disasters, victims of social conflict, and other minorities. If Indonesia particularly Jakarta is to implement inclusive education meaningfully, institutions in education system need to revise their value system, restructure their organization and requirement procedures to overcome an obstacle to learning and participation for the full range of children in Indonesia.

Inclusive education is a new discourse in Indonesia education system and is treated as an additional program in the education sector which only be handled by a small number of personnel. If the government and other educational institutions very concern with this program and had a good infrastructure (i.e. better funded, better controlled and supported by law), positive results might occur for all learners. As a next step, the government should develop and support the formation of non-profit organisations, incorporating professionals, parents, and academicians as a main place source for information provision and in controlling the implementation of inclusive education in schools.

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